

Calibrating Position and Force in an Optical-Trap System for Nanomechanical Studies of Individual Protein Molecules

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Abstract. Optical traps are invaluable tools in molecular biophysics, for they permit the precise measurement of the mechanical properties and dynamics of individual biomolecules. Accurate calibrations of both position and force are critical to such measurements. This manuscript presents a comprehensive protocol for calibrating an optical-trap system designed to study the nanomechanics of individual protein molecules. We describe an apparatus that involves dual optical traps and detail a sequence of calibration and correction steps that address hardware nonlinearities and multiple error sources. The protocol emphasizes the use of *in situ* linearization of the position detector and power-spectral analysis to calibrate the position and spring constants of the optical trap. By ensuring high-precision measurements of position and force, this protocol might prove a useful resource for researchers in the field of molecular biophysics.

Optical traps¹ have become essential and powerful tools for studying the nanomechanical properties of single molecules. By employing strongly focused laser beams to trap and manipulate individual particles, these systems facilitate detailed investigations into the mechanical properties of the molecules attached to the particles. Accurate calibration of both position and force in these systems is crucial to ensure experimental reliability and reproducibility. By addressing common challenges such as hardware non-linearity and environmental noise, this manuscript presents a comprehensive protocol for calibrating position and force in an optical trap. We will introduce our apparatus, provide an overview of the calibration steps, and offer detailed information on key calibration and correction processes.

Our system integrates two optical traps² (Fig. 1A). The biomolecule subjected to force spectroscopy experiments is tethered between an immobile, 1.5 μm -diameter pedestal bead and a mobile, 1.0 μm -diameter probe bead. The system's position-sensing capabilities depend upon a 1064 nm laser beam that forms a weak optical trap to confine the probe bead. Coupled with a quadrant photodiode (QPD) serving as the position detector, this configuration allows for precise measurements of three-dimensional position of the probe bead with subnanometer spatial resolution and microsecond temporal resolution. A powerful 852 nm laser beam forms a second, force-producing trap that can be displaced several hundred nanometers radially from the position-sensing trap in order to generate sufficient force on the probe bead (Fig. 1B). By modulating this laser's intensity, the force exerted on the probe bead, and thereby on the tethered molecule, can be meticulously controlled.

Two critical factors are essential to studying the nanomechanics of a biomolecule: the force applied to the molecule and the corresponding change in the molecule's end-to-end distance, which is derived from the relative positions of the probe beads. Both of these elements must be measured with high precision and carefully calibrated to correct for noise, hardware nonlinearity, and other error sources.

Overview of calibration steps

1. Calibrate the laser modulator for the force-producing laser to ensure precise control of its spring constant (Section 2a).
2. Turn on the position-sensing beam and capture a freely diffusing probe bead deep within the solution.
3. Calibrate the position detector to convert SY , the response signal along the y -axis, from voltages into real position signals y in nanometers (Section 1a).

4. Correct for position detector sensitivity using power spectral density analysis (Section 3a).
5. Calibrate the beam steering of the force-producing trap's position (Section 2b).
6. Calibrate the spring constant of the force-producing trap (Section 2c) and record any focus shifts at varying laser intensities (Section 4a).
7. While moving the probe bead close to the coverslip where pedestal beads tethered with molecules are located, ensure that both types of beads are at the same equatorial height.
8. Correct for the close-to-coverslip position signal errors (Section 3b).
9. Select a relatively isolated pedestal bead.
10. Correct for the light scattered by a selected pedestal bead (Section 3c).
11. Slowly bring the selected pedestal bead closer to the probe bead and observe the formation of a molecular tether by means of thermal-noise imaging³. If no tether forms, select another pedestal bead and repeat calibration step 9.
12. If a stable tether forms, various experiments—for example, force-ramp and force-clamp experiments—can be performed to study the nanomechanics of the molecule.
13. Repeat steps 2-10 for any subsequent experiments.

FIGURE 1. Force spectroscopy apparatus. A: Schematic diagram of the optical-trap system. The purple line indicates the force-producing laser beam, the red line the position-sensing laser beam, and the grey dashed line represents the brightfield LED illumination. Key components include the Faraday isolators (FI), half-wave ($\lambda/2$) and quarter-wave ($\lambda/4$) plates, polarizing (PBS) and non-polarizing (BS) beam splitters, single (SPD) and quadrant (QPD) photodiodes, dichroic mirrors (DM), and neutral density (ND) filters. B: Schematic diagram of force generation in single-molecule force spectroscopy experiments. The upper panel depicts the arrangement after formation of a molecule tether—the grey line between the two beads—but before the application of force. The probe bead is positioned approximately 90 nm from the center of the position-sensing trap by moving the sample stage. This initial positioning ensures that entire displacement range of the probe bead remains within the linear range of the position detector. The lower panel shows the state when the force-producing beam is activated and displaced $L = 200$ nm from the position-sensing trap in the positive direction, exerting force on the probe bead. The force exerted can be calculated by $F = k \cdot (L - y)$, in which k is the spring constant of the force-producing trap.

1. Position detection

(a) Calibration of the non-linear position detector

For position detection, although the same principles apply to the x -axis, we concentrate on the axis along which the experiments are performed, the y -axis. The position of the probe bead is measured by a quadrant photodiode (QPD), which detects the forward-scattered light from the position-sensing laser (Fig. 1A). The response signals, SY , from the detector exhibit non-linearity relative to the actual positions, y . A common method of calibrating the position detector is the fixed-particle-scan (FPS) technique⁴. This method involves anchoring a probe bead on the coverslip, focusing the position-sensing trap on this bead, and moving the bead known distances with the sample stage. This process records the response signals, SY , thus establishing a relationship between SY and the actual position y (Fig. 2A). From Fig. 2A, we can infer that for a 1 μm -diameter bead, there is a critical region, $\Delta y \approx 300$ nm, over which the detector's response is linear, which is also the range primarily used in most of the force spectroscopy experiments.

However, the FPS method has major limitations due to the immobilization of the probe bead and the potential optical interferences at the bead-coverslip interface, which can alter the detector's response by approximately 10 %⁵⁻⁸. To address this, we implement an *in-situ* linearization method, determining local detector sensitivities by comparing the measured local diffusion constant from Brownian motion to the theoretical diffusion constant⁵. Although the bead is confined within the harmonic position-sensing trap, it diffuses freely on a very short timescale, t , that is much smaller than the position autocorrelation time⁹ τ of the position-sensing trap. In our system, $\tau_{x,y} \approx 2$ ms for the lateral axes and $\tau_z \approx 9$ ms along the optical axis. For chosen time lags $t_{x,y} = 30$ μs and $t_z = 150$ μs , the one-dimensional mean squared displacement (MSD) of the bead exhibits free Brownian motion¹⁰ equal to $2Dt$. From this value we can calculate the local diffusion constant $D_{local}(SY_0)$ for each position on the detector within its measurement bin $SY_0 \pm \Delta SY$, in which SY_0 is the position on the detector and ΔSY is a selected bin size. By comparing the local diffusion constant $D_{local}(SY_0)$ in units of $\text{V}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ to the theoretical diffusion constant D_{theo} in $\text{nm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, we derive the local sensitivity of the detector:

$$\beta_{local} = \frac{\partial SY}{\partial y} \Big|_{SY_0} = \sqrt{\frac{2 \cdot D_{local}(SY_0) \cdot t}{2 \cdot D_{theo} \cdot t}} = \sqrt{\frac{MSD_{local}(SY_0, t)}{2 \cdot D_{theo} \cdot t}}. \quad (1)$$

Here β_{local} represents the local detector sensitivity, SY is the QPD's voltage output, y is the position in nanometers, and $D_{theo} = \frac{k_B T}{\gamma_0}$ with k_B the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, and γ_0 the friction coefficient. We can reconstruct the real position of the probe bead, $y(SY)$, by integration:

$$\int \frac{1}{\beta_{local}} dSY = y(SY) + constant. \quad (2)$$

Finally, by fitting a five-degree polynomial function to $y(SY) = C_1 + C_2 SY + \dots + C_6 SY^5$, we address the nonlinearity of the QPD detector. This step allows us to translate the voltage signals into actual positions in nanometers (Fig. 2B). Note that this *in situ* calibration applies predominantly within the linear region of the detector (Fig. 2A-B) over which $y(SY)$ typically approximates a linear relationship.

2. Force generation

(a) Calibration of the laser modulator

The laser modulator plays a crucial role in adjusting the intensity of the 852 nm force-producing laser, which directly influences the spring constant of the trap. By incrementally increasing the voltage sent to the modulator, the single photodiode (SPD) senses the relative intensity of the output laser beam, denoted as I . The response curve (Fig. 2D) is typically modeled using a cosine function. This model allows us to find the maximum possible intensity of the laser as well as to establish the relationship between the command voltage and the response intensity I . For precise control of the laser intensity, we either revert the intensity measurements to the command voltages using the cosine model or employ a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller. In the PID setup, the commanded laser intensity acts as the setpoint, whereas the intensity readout from the SPD acts a process variable that enables dynamic adjustments based on real-time feedback.

(b) *Calibration of the position steering of the force-producing trap*

To effectively generate force on the probe bead, the force-producing trap must be radially displaced from the probe bead. This displacement is facilitated by moving the steering lens perpendicularly to the optical axis using a three-dimensional piezoelectric nanopositioner. The actual displacement of the force-producing trap is inferred from the observed displacement of the probe bead, for this trap exerts a significantly stronger force than the position-sensing trap. The displacement, denoted as L , exhibits a linear relationship with the command voltage applied to the nanopositioner. By systematically varying the voltages to the piezoelectric nanopositioner and monitoring the corresponding position displacement of the probe bead, we establish a standard linear calibration curve that guides the precise steering of the trap (Fig. 2F).

(c) *Calibration of the spring constant of the force-producing trap*

Calibrating the spring constant of a harmonic trap can be achieved through several methods. One approach involves fitting the motion of the confined bead using an autocorrelation function to extract the spring constant from the autocorrelation time $\tau = \frac{\gamma_0}{k}$ ¹¹. Alternatively, Boltzmann statistics may be applied to relate the position probability

density $\rho(y)$ of the probe bead to the potential energy $E(y)$ of the harmonic trap along the y -axis: $\rho(y) = Ae^{-\frac{E(y)}{k_B T}} = A \cdot e^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2}ky^2}{k_B T}}$, in which A is a normalization constant.

In our protocol, we employ another method that involves fitting the power-spectral density (PSD) of the position signals, $P_{hydro}(f)$, to a hydrodynamically correct theory¹²:

$$P_{hydro}(f) = \frac{D/\pi^2 [1+(f/f_v)^2]^{\frac{1}{3}}}{(f_c - f^{\frac{3}{2}}/f_v^{\frac{1}{2}} - f^2/f_m)^2 + (f + f^{\frac{3}{2}}/f_v^{\frac{1}{2}})^2}, \quad (3)$$

in which $f_c = \frac{k}{2\pi\gamma_0}$ is the corner frequency, D is the diffusion coefficient in $V^2 \cdot s^{-1}$, m is the mass of the bead, r is the radius of the bead, ρ is the mass density of the surrounding liquid, η is its dynamic viscosity, and $f_m = \frac{\gamma_0}{2\pi(m + \frac{2\pi\rho r^3}{3})}$,

$$f_v = \frac{\eta}{\rho\pi r^2}.$$

We begin an experiment by aligning the force-producing trap with the position-sensing trap that has a captured probe bead. We then incrementally increase the intensity I of the force-producing laser by 10 % of its maximum intensity at each step, recording the thermal motion of the trapped probe bead. At each intensity level, we extract the spring constant k of the trap from the corner frequency $f_c = \frac{k}{2\pi\gamma_0}$ by fitting the PSD of the recorded thermal motion to the Equation 3. This process establishes a linear relationship between spring constants and intensities of the force-producing trap, $k(I)$ (Fig. 2E).

3. Position correction

(a) *Correction for detector sensitivity by power-spectral analysis*

Following the identification of non-linearity of the position detector, we successfully convert signals from voltages to nanometers. However, the derived position $y(SY)$ deviates by around 8.5 % from the accurate position verified by the CCD camera (Fig. 2C). This deviation likely results from non-diffusion-related noise accumulated during the integration part of the calibration. To address this issue, we employ power-spectral analysis (*Section 2c*) to accurately determine the actual sensitivity, β_{PSD} , of the detector within its linear region. This process involves strongly confining the probe bead at the center of the position-sensing beam with the force-producing trap and fitting the PSD of the position data by equation (3). From this model we extract the diffusion constant for the linear region, D_{PSD} .

If the initial detector calibration was accurate, the sensitivity at the linear region, β_{PSD} , which can be calculated using D_{PSD} in units of $V^2 \cdot s^{-1}$ by

$$\beta_{PSD} = \sqrt{\frac{D_{PSD}}{D_{theo}}} \quad (4)$$

should accord well with the local sensitivity $\beta_{local} = \frac{1}{C_2}$ in the linear region, where C_2 is the linear coefficient of $y(SY)$. Any discrepancies can be adjusted with a correction scaling factor α_{PSD} , defined by the ratio between the two

sensitivities $\alpha_{PSD} = \frac{\beta_{local}}{\beta_{PSD}} = \frac{1}{c_2} \sqrt{\frac{D_{theo}}{D_{PSD}}}$. Implementing this correction reduces the positional error to approximately 3.4 % (Fig. 2C) and significantly enhances the accuracy of our measurements.

(b) Correction for the close-to-coverslip position error

Although calibration of the position detector is typically carried out deep in the solution—over 10 μm away from the coverslip—the actual experiments are conducted much closer to the coverslip, approximately 250 nm away. The optical effects of the coverslip on the position signal are significant and cannot be overlooked⁵⁻⁸. To quantify and correct this error, the following method is employed. First, record the mean position y_0 of the probe bead when it is positioned 250 nm away from the coverslip. Subsequently, displace the force-producing trap from $L = 0$ to $L = 100$ nm and record the new mean position y_1 . The scale factor $\alpha_{coverslip}$ for correcting this error can then be calculated using the ratio $\alpha_{coverslip} = \frac{100}{|y_1 - y_0|}$. This scale factor is critical for adjusting the experimental data to account for the proximity of the coverslip and thus for ensuring the accuracy of our measurements.

FIGURE 2. Exemplary calibration results. A: The response curve for the position detector along the y -axis, as obtained through the fixed-particle-scan method. The grey line indicates the linear range ($\Delta y \approx 300$ nm) centered on the QPD. B: Local detector sensitivities are represented by grey circles calculated from local Brownian motion data. Orange disks illustrate the real positions of the probe bead, reconstructed from measured signals (SY) on the detector. This plot highlights that *in situ* calibration was primarily restricted in the detector’s linear range, which is adequate for our experiments which operate within $\Delta y < 300$ nm. C: Comparison of the accuracies of position signals with and without PSD correction. Each pair of data points represents an individual probe bead ($N = 8$). Percentage errors without correction show a mean of $8.5\% \pm 1.6\%$ (mean \pm SE), whereas with PSD correction errors fall to $3.4\% \pm 0.9\%$. D: Measurement of the force-producing laser intensities by means of the SPD, modulated by varying the voltage to the laser modulator. The grey line indicates a cosine fit to the data. E: Linear dependence of the spring constants of the force-producing trap on the applied optical power along three perpendicular axes. F: Linear control over the displacement L of the force-producing trap center from the center of the position-sensing trap achieved by adjusting the steering lens with a piezoelectric nanopositioner.

(c) Correction for light scattered by the pedestal bead³

In force spectroscopy experiments, the proximity between the probe bead and the pedestal bead—often less than a few hundred nanometers—results in significant scattering of the position-sensing light by the pedestal bead. To

accurately correct for this effect, the pedestal bead is first moved several micrometers away from the probe bead. The force-producing beam is then displaced from $L = 0$ to $L = +100$ nm to stabilize the probe bead's position at +100 nm relative to the position-sensing laser, and the zero offset voltage signals SY_{probe_0} are recorded.

The pedestal bead is subsequently brought closer to the probe bead at which the experiment will be conducted. The pedestal bead is then moved by the sample stage to scan the operational area surrounding that bead. During this scanning process, the total position signals from the probe bead, along with the contribution from the pedestal bead, are recorded as $SY_{total}(b)$, in which b represents the position coordinates of the pedestal bead on the sample stage. The combined signal can be expressed as $SY_{total}(b) = SY_{pedestal}(b) + SY_{probe_0}$, which permits the determination of $SY_{pedestal}(b)$ for each coordinate of the pedestal bead.

During the subsequent experimental step meant of forming a molecular tether between the probe and pedestal beads, the probe bead is positioned at the center of the position-sensing trap ($L = 0$). If a tether forms successfully, the current coordinates of the pedestal bead, $b_{current}$, are interpolated to the two-dimensional matrix of $SY_{pedestal}(b)$. From this we can determine the actual probe bead signal, SY_{probe} , by subtracting pedestal's contribution $SY_{pedestal}(b_{current})$ from the total signal $SY_{total}(b_{current})$. This procedure accurately isolates the probe bead's position signals from the scattering effects of the pedestal bead and thereby effectively corrects the positional signals on the QPD detector.

4. Force correction

(a) Correction for focus shifts in the force-producing trap

During the calibration of the spring constant of the force-producing trap at various intensity levels (*Section 2c*) we observed focus shifts of a few nanometers corresponding to changes in intensity. These shifts likely result from minor deviations from the Gaussian distribution of the beam profile after it exits the laser modulator. Such deviations can introduce errors in force calculations by affecting the distance L between the force-producing and position-sensing traps. To compensate for these discrepancies, we record the focus shifts, denoted as d , at each laser intensity I , and thus establish a relationship between intensity and focus shifts, $d(I)$. When applying a force to the probe bead, the SPD reads out the intensities of the force-producing laser, allowing us to estimate the focus shift at each data point by interpolating the intensities to $d(I)$. This correction ensures accuracy in our force measurements by compensating for any variability of the beam's focus.

Summary of calibrations and corrections outcomes

The comprehensive set of calibrations and corrections applied throughout our experiments enables precise and accurate calculations of both the position and force exerted on the probe bead in our optical tweezer system. Integrating all adjustments, the final calibrated position of the probe bead can be expressed by the following equation:

$$y_{calibrated} = y([SY_{total} - SY_{pedestal}(b_{current})]) \cdot \alpha_{PSD} \cdot \alpha_{coverslip}. \quad (5)$$

By accounting for position correction derived from power-spectral analysis, close-to-coverslip effects, and pedestal-bead light-scattering effect, this relationship ensures that the position data are accurate and representative of the actual experimental conditions.

The calibrated force exerted on the probe bead is given by:

$$F_{calibrated} = k(I) \cdot (L + d(I) - y_{calibrated}). \quad (6)$$

By ensuring that the force calculations incorporate dynamic adjustments for beam focus shifts and the final calibrated position from Equation 5, this formula significantly enhances the reliability and accuracy of our force measurements.

Through the detailed procedures outlined, our protocol ensures that both position and force measurements are adjusted to reflect true experimental values. Our approach facilitates more accurate studies of the mechanical properties and dynamics of biomolecules under force.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors thank Tobias F. Bartsch for designing and establishing the experimental apparatus, Camila M. Villasante for help with some experiments, and Brian A. Fabella for technical assistance. X.D. is supported by institutional funds from the Rockefeller University. A.J.H is an Investigator of Howard Hughes Medical Institute.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Haosheng Wen] Can you comment on the generality of the protocol presented in this paper? Which parts can be used for typical setups? In addition, what other systems, beside protocadherin-15, could be explored? Are there limitations to take into considerations for other systems? (let's say cadherin-23 or the whole tip link). Also, you used a five-degree polynomial function to fit the function $y(SY)$, which is the real position of the probe bead. We are wondering how accurate is this fit function with well-tuned parameters (or can you comment more on the process to obtain those parameters?). Is there a specific reason that you chose the five-degree polynomial to fit the $y(SY)$?

[Xinyue Deng] In principle, our setups are applicable to a broad range of proteins. However, the key consideration is the requirement for specific molecular tethers at the two ends of a protein molecule. In our experiments, we used biotin-streptavidin and SpyTag-SpyCatcher pairs to ensure specific and strong interactions between the protein ends and the probe and pedestal beads. Although the protocol is versatile, applying it to proteins that require high forces exceeding 100 pN would present challenges. The force can be modulated both by the intensity of the force-producing laser and by the displacement L between the two lasers. However, there is a limit to how much force can be produced on the probe bead, which is constrained by the power limit of the laser and by the working distance of the force-producing trap.

To evaluate the accuracy of the fit, we calculated the goodness-of-fit metrics, including the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the root-mean-squared error (RMSE) for the example data shown in the figure below. For this fit, the polynomial model is $y = 79.54 + 53.24 * SY - 0.4483 * SY^2 - 0.1874 * SY^3 - 0.002509 * SY^4 + 0.09544 * SY^5$. The goodness-of-fit metrics indicate a good fit: the polynomial model displays minimal deviation from a linear model. These results confirm that the detector's calibration is successful and the sample is suitable for further experiments.

[Dáibhid Ó Maoiléidigh] Using force ramp to stimulate the tip link construct, do you think you might be over estimating the stiffness of the gating spring or the tip link due to time-dependent forces, such as viscous forces? Or is your force static? Do you have a way to estimate and provide a correction for this?

[Xinyue Deng] Similar to the observations by Dr. Martin and Dr. Tobin, we see a consistent trend, and the stiffness values accord well with theirs. The results presented in this talk were not obtained in an equilibrium state. However, we have tried a low loading rate—approximately $1.5 \text{ pN} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ —and obtained stiffness values similar to those for a loading rate of $130 \text{ pN} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. At present we are also working on equilibrium measurements of the mechanical and kinetics parameters, and we hope to correct for any potential overestimation of the stiffness.

[Martin Göpfert] Have you checked for the consequences on the tip link's length? Have you done electron microscopy to examine it, and do you see elongation of the protein? If there is unfolding in the protein, do you observe it in the tip link under EM?

[Xinyue Deng] We routinely conducted transmission electron microscopy on our PCDH15 constructs to ensure that they are homogenous and of appropriate dimensions. However, during these EM experiments, we did not apply force to the two ends of the protein. Although we observed in electron micrographs that the mutated PCDH15 appeared to be more flexible than the control protein, we did not observe any unfolding when the proteins were not subjected to force.